

165 GHz to 220 GHz Broadband Amplifier with ± 0.75 -dB Gain Variation and Minimum Group Delay Variation in SiGe BiCMOS

Xun Chen, Jonas Winkelhake, Muh-Dey Wei, Renato Negra

Chair of High Frequency Electronics
RWTH Aachen University, 52062 Aachen, Germany
Email: xun.chen@hfe.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract— This paper presents a broadband amplifier with gain variation less than ± 0.75 dB and small group delay variation over the frequency band from 165 GHz to 220 GHz. To achieve the small gain variation over the broad bandwidth, multiple amplification stages which peak at different frequencies are commonly used. However, in this work a common broadband amplification stage is focused for its flexibility and scalability. In the common stage, the broadband matching is obtained by manipulating the inband admittance, Y , to traverse the real axis of Y -Smith chart, and offsetting the susceptance over frequency with a resonant circuit incorporating a shorted stub and the parasitic collector capacitance. Gain flatness of cascaded stages is enhanced by introducing mismatch in the common stage. The gain of an entire amplifier can be further increased by cascading stages without other efforts such as interstage matching, with similar inband performance of gain and group delay variation. A prototype cascades three stages to achieve 10-dB gain and 55-GHz bandwidth with low power consumption of 28 mW in measurements. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the presented amplifier achieves the smallest gain variation and group delay variation in G-band.

Keywords— millimetre-wave, G-band, SiGe, BiCMOS, MMIC, gain flatness, group delay, broadband amplifier, wireless communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Millimetre-wave (mm-wave) frequency bands offer the opportunity for high-data-rate wireless communication such as beyond 5G and 6G. The silicon platform is one of the most attracting candidates to implement mm-wave systems for its low cost and high integration capability. Broadband amplifier is one of the critical components in such systems which should provide both sufficient power gain and bandwidth (BW). Gain flatness is one of the important performance matrices which ensures low distortion of the modulated signal, and releases the dynamic range requirement of data converters.

Several circuit topologies have been proposed for broadband amplifier design. One famous topology is the distributed amplifier [1][2], which provides significant BW over decades, but occupies large chip size as well as power consumption. In addition, in bipolar transistor designs, the parasitic base resistance, R_b , degrades the performance severely.

Multiband matching is another option to achieve gain flatness over broad BW [3][4][5][6]. It cascades a number of

Fig. 1. Gain flatness approach: (a) multiband matching, and (b) broadband cascaded.

stages which are peaked at different frequencies, as illustrated in Fig. 1a. The main challenge of this topology is that it requires delicate input, output and multiple interstage matching networks to obtain gain flatness over frequencies. It becomes more difficult for mm-wave designs due to the requirements of precise models, intensive electromagnetic (EM) simulations as well as fabrication deviation. Besides, this topology cannot be scalable in terms of gain.

Alternatively, a broadband stage, which focuses on superior gain flatness and group delay, can be designed, and then cascaded depending on the required gain. The proposed design cascades three identical stages, and each stage provides flat gain response over frequencies, as shown in Fig. 1b. The advantage is that it can easily obtain higher gain by cascading more stages while keeping the gain flatness. This approach is similar to an off-the-shelf high-gain amplifier design. However, it is to the best of the authors' knowledge the first time to employ this technique for a broadband mm-wave amplifier demonstrating the superior gain and group delay variation.

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

A conceptual schematic of the broadband amplifier is shown in Fig. 2. It is composed of an input and output matching network, and numbers of broadband amplification stages.

To design a broadband amplification stage is the main challenge in such an approach. In general, the cascode topology in an amplification stage is preferable in this process for mm-wave designs due to the high gain of the common-base (CB) transistor. However, the CB in the cascode

Fig. 2. Conceptual schematic of the broadband amplifier.

topology suffers from a low output impedance, resulting in a complicated broadband matching network, and may degrade the output reflection coefficient in the frequency band of interest. Thus, each broadband stage is composed of two common-emitter (CE) transistors, Q_1 and Q_2 .

The broadband matching network of the amplification stage is described in Fig. 3. Since each stage is cascaded, the output load impedance of each stage is the input impedance of the following one, as shown in Fig. 2. The admittance at node A is thus capacitive over the frequency band from 165 GHz to 240 GHz as plotted in Fig. 3a. Note that it indicates that the output matching network (OMN) for a complete amplifier shown in Fig. 2 has to present the similar capacitive load to the stage.

The open stub, TL_1 , in combination with the series transmission line (TL), TL_2 , is used to manipulate the admittance to obtain a desired response over frequency as shown in the admittance of node B, which is capacitive below 200 GHz, and inductive above 200 GHz. The susceptance offsetting network is composed of a shorted stub, TL_3 , and the parasitic collector capacitance, C_{ce1} . TL_3 can be considered as a varied inductor with frequency, which has a varied quality factor, Q , because of its series resistance and the parasitic resistance from the DC decoupling capacitor, C_d . C_{ce1} is related to the selected transistor, and has insignificant change over the frequency of interest according to simulation. This parallel-connected network offsets the susceptance portion of the admittance at node B, and keeps the admittance unchanged at 200 GHz. It provides a negative susceptance below 200 GHz, and a positive susceptance above 200 GHz. This means that the capacitive part of the admittance locus at node B moves upwards to the real axis, and the inductive part of the locus moves downwards in the Y -Smith chart. This results in a broadband performance as shown in the admittance at node IN.

The similar approach is taken for the input side of transistor Q_1 as denoted as node A', node B', and node IN'. As shown in Fig. 3b, TL_4 and TL_5 move the inductive admittance at the low end of frequency band to the capacitive region of the Y -Smith chart, and the capacitive admittance at the high end

Fig. 3. Node admittances from 165 GHz to 240 GHz in Y -Smith chart.

Fig. 4. Simulated available gain and mismatch loss of a broadband stage.

of frequency band to the inductive region. The red locus passes through the real axis of Y -Smith chart at 230 GHz, indicating that a higher midband frequency should be considered for the susceptance offsetting network. Therefore, transistor Q_2 is selected to have a smaller C_{ce} . The resulting admittance at node IN' after susceptance offset is shown in Fig. 3b. Q_1 is selected to have three multipliers, with an emitter area, A_E , of $3 \times 0.07 \times 0.9 \mu\text{m}^2$. Q_2 is selected to have two multipliers.

In order to improve the overall gain flatness when a number of stages are cascaded, interstage mismatch is introduced within the broadband stage, by properly determining TL_7 at the input, and the capacitance, C_1 , at the output. As shown in

Fig. 5. Simulated S -parameters with different numbers of cascaded broadband stages.

Fig. 6. Chip photograph of the broadband amplifier under test.

Fig. 4, the relatively high available gain of a stage is suppressed by a high mismatch loss at low frequencies. As the available gain approaches a constant value at high frequencies, the mismatch loss becomes simultaneously a relatively constant value.

The concept of the interstage mismatch is verified by the simulated S -parameters with different numbers of cascaded broadband stages, as shown in Fig. 5. The input and output are matched to 50Ω with the matching networks shown in Fig. 2. It is shown that the inband gain variation remains small, e.g., from ± 0.65 dB for a two-cascaded-stage amplifier, to ± 1.4 dB for a five-cascaded-stage one. All of the simulated cascaded amplifiers show unconditional stability. It is indicated that the gain of the proposed amplifier can be easily further increased by cascading more broadband stages, with the advantage of less design efforts compared to the multiband matching method, where new interstage matching networks are required with a different center frequency allocation, when more stages should be included to improve the overall inband gain flatness. A maximum of nine cascaded stages was simulated and found to be unconditionally stable. It is the tradeoff between chip size, DC power consumption, peak gain, and maximum allowance of gain flatness. A three-cascaded-stage prototype is used to proof the concept due to the size limitation.

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The proposed amplifier is fabricated in a 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS technology from IHP featuring a transistor maximum unity-current-gain cutoff frequency, f_T , of 300 GHz and maximum oscillation frequency, f_{max} , of 450 GHz. It is implemented with on-chip grounded coplanar waveguide (GCPW) TLs, and on-chip distributed DC decoupling

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Measured and simulated S -parameters from 140 GHz to 220 GHz, and (b) measured stability factors.

Fig. 8. Measured and simulated group delay from 140 GHz to 220 GHz.

capacitors as C_d . The input impedance of C_d is taken into account to design the broadband stage, and the values over frequency are verified by a fabricated test structure reported in [9].

A photograph of the chip under test is shown in Fig. 6. The amplifier including measurement pads occupies an area of $1.65 \text{ mm} \times 0.47 \text{ mm}$. All base terminals are biased at 0.9 V. Each broadband stage draws 7.8 mA from a 1.2-V DC supply, leading to a total DC power consumption of 28 mW.

The on-wafer measurement environment is set up with a Keysight network analyzer PNA-X, frequency extender VDI VNAX Mini WR5.1, and probes i220-S-GSG-BT by Formfactor. The parasitic effects of the measurement pads are de-embedded with an on-wafer through-reflect-line (TRL) structure.

Table 1. COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART BROADBAND AMPLIFIERS USING 130-NM SiGe BiCMOS

Reference	Topology	Bandwidth (GHz)	Max. inband $ \Gamma $ (dB)	Gain (dB)	Gain flatness (dB)	Δ Group delay (ps)	P_{DC} (mW)	Area (mm ²)
[5]	CE, multiband matching	140-220	-1 ⁺	12.5-15.5	± 1.5	n/a	46	0.7
[6]	CE+CB, multiband matching	173-207	-5 ⁺	20.5-23.5	± 1.5	n/a	3.2	1.05
[7]	CE+CB, broadband matching	185-205*	-7	20-22.5	± 1.25	7 ⁺	70.2	0.88
[8]	CB, balanced	155-210*	-10	7-10	± 1.5	n/a	16.8	0.8
This work	CE, broadband matching	165-220	-7	8.5-10	± 0.75	3.5	28	0.78

⁺ Graphical estimation. ^{*} Defined with both $|S_{11}|$ and $|S_{22}|$ smaller than -7 dB.

The measured and simulated S -parameters are presented in Fig. 7. The simulations plotted here are obtained from Keysight ADS together with Momentum EM simulator. Within the BW between 165 GHz and 220 GHz, where both $|S_{11}|$ and $|S_{22}|$ are below -7 dB, the amplifier achieves a gain variation less than ± 0.75 dB. A maximum measured gain of 10 dB is reached at 165 GHz. Unconditional stability of the amplifier is indicated in Fig. 7b. K -factor is above 1, and $|\Delta|$ is less than 1 in the entire G-band.

Fig. 8 shows the measured and simulated group delays of the amplifier. An inband group delay variation of 3.5 ps is obtained in measurement, corresponding well to the simulation. When more stages are cascaded in the amplifier, e.g., from two cascaded stages to five cascaded stages, the group delay variation remains below 6 ps in simulation.

A comparison with state-of-the-art broadband amplifiers using 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS is made in Table 1. As can be seen this work achieves the minimum gain variation and group delay within the BW. Importantly, this topology has the scalability to adapt with system requirements without much design effort among all other approaches.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a broadband amplifier with gain variation less than ± 0.75 dB and small group delay variation over the frequency band from 165 GHz to 220 GHz is demonstrated.

The gain flatness is achieved with common broadband amplification stages. The broadband stage is designed with susceptance offset. Further gain improvement is feasible if more broadband stages are cascaded. The small group delay variation, flexibility and scalability of the amplifier are beneficial to transceiver systems in G-band.

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